

Synthesis of Some New Dithiocarbamates as Potential Insecticides and Agricultural and Garden Fungicides

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Manuscript received 13 October 1980, revised 9 March 1981, accepted 13 April 1981

Several new [(substituted-2-benzothiazolyl) carbamoyl]methyl dithiocarbamates and [(substituted-2-benzothiazolyl) carbamoyl]methyl-*o*, *m* or *p*-chloro dithiocarbamates have been prepared by condensing the ammonium salt of aryl dithiocarbamic acid with chloroacetyl amino (substituted) benzothiazoles in dry acetone. Their structure was established on the basis of ir and nmr spectra and elemental analysis. Some of them show insecticidal and fungicidal properties.

DITHIOCARBAMATES have attracted the attention of several workers on account of their wide ranging biological activities. The activity is attributed to their structure complementarity to the active site of acetyl cholinesterase and their consequent action as substrates with low turn over numbers. It was in 1931 that Dupont Co. showed that some of the derivatives of dithiocarbamic acid have fungicidal and insecticidal activities¹⁻³. Since then several activities have been tested in dithiocarbamate derivatives. Potent herbicides⁴⁻⁵, insecticides⁶, pesticides^{7,8} and nematocides containing dithiocarbamate group have been reported. 'Baygon', a common commercial insecticide is a carbamate derivative: (2-isopropoxyphenyl-N-methyl carbamate). Acaricidal⁹ and anthelmintic¹⁰ activities have also been successfully tested in them. The use of certain dithiocarbamates as radioprotective drugs^{11,12} has added more importance to this system.

Keeping in view the wide spectrum activities new [(substituted-2-benzothiazolyl)carbamoyl]methyl dithiocarbamates and [(substituted-2-benzothiazolyl)carbamoyl]methyl-*o*, *m* or *p*-chlorodithiocarbamates have been prepared by condensing the ammonium salt of substituted phenyl dithiocarbamic acid¹³ with different chloroacetyl amino (substituted) benzothiazoles in dry acetone. The various substituents in the benzothiazole nucleus are expected to enhance lipoid solubility of the drug and increase its potency.

The structure of the reported compounds was confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis, ir¹⁴ and nmr spectra. Characteristic peaks were observed at ≈ 1715 (s), ($\nu_{C=O}$), 1625(s), ($\nu_{C=N}$), 1060(m), ($\nu_{C=S}$) cm^{-1} .

All compounds were synthesised according to the following Scheme.

Synthesis and screening of [(substituted-2-benzothiazolyl)carbamoyl]methyl dithiocarbamates and [(substituted-2-benzothiazolyl)carbamoyl]methyl-*o*, *m* or *p*-chlorodithiocarbamates as fungicides and insecticides are reported in this communication.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary in liquid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer Model Nos. 621 and 720 and nmr spectra on Varian A60D in CDCl_3 . A Coleman Analyser was used for elemental analysis.

Substituted 2-aminobenzothiazoles: Substituted 2-aminobenzothiazoles were prepared by the oxidation of asymmetrical aryl thioureas with liquid bromine in chloroform¹⁵.

2-Chloroacetyl amino (substituted) benzothiazoles: 2-Aminobenzothiazole (0.01 M) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 M) were refluxed in benzene for 2 hrs on a water bath. Excess benzene was distilled off and the product was washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and distilled water. It was dried and recrystallised from ethanol to obtain a pure sample of the required compound.

Similarly other chloroacetyl derivatives of substituted benzothiazoles were prepared by the method of Bhargava *et al*¹⁶.

Ammonium salt of dithiocarbamic acid: The ammonium salt of aryl dithiocarbamic acid was prepared by stirring a mixture of the amine in carbon disulphide and ammonia in ice bath till a crystalline precipitate of the required product was obtained¹³.

TABLE 1—[(SUBSTITUTED-2-BENZOTHAZOLYL)CARBAMOYL]METHYL (OR *o,m,p*-CHLORO)DITHIOCARBANILATES

Sl. No.	Substituents		Molecular Formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	Carbon%		Hydrogen%	
	X	Y				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	H	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS ₂	72	160	53.27	54.49	3.60	3.62
2.	4-Me	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS ₂	70	155	54.42	54.60	4.16	4.02
3.	5-Me	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS ₂	81	158	54.50	54.60	4.18	4.02
4.	6-Me	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS ₂	75	145	54.80	54.60	4.20	4.02
5.	4-Cl	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS ₂	72	149	48.63	48.79	3.15	3.05
6.	5-Cl	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS ₂	80	138	48.54	48.79	3.19	3.05
7.	6-Cl	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS ₂	58	133	48.70	48.79	3.03	3.05
8.	6-MeO	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	69	126	51.45	51.15	3.62	3.80
9.	6-EtO	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	72	130	53.48	53.59	4.90	4.22
10.	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS ₂	74	100	51.01	50.86	3.15	3.05
11.	4-Me	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	79	95	50.01	50.06	3.70	3.44
12.	5-Me	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	75	107	50.22	50.03	3.56	3.44
13.	6-Me	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	77	98	50.32	50.06	3.60	3.44
14.	4-Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	69	125	46.45	46.6	2.53	2.67
15.	5-Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	66	110	46.53	46.6	2.85	2.67
16.	6-MeO	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	80	105	48.96	48.17	3.22	3.81
17.	6-EtO	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	78	120	49.49	49.37	3.53	3.65
18.	4-Me	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	68	101	49.92	50.03	3.49	3.44
19.	5-Me	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	73	103	49.89	50.03	3.31	3.44
20.	6-Me	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	71	112	50.12	50.06	3.29	3.44
21.	4-Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	73	105	44.96	44.86	2.50	2.57
22.	5-Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	76	97	44.74	44.86	2.69	2.57
23.	6-Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	72	92	44.79	44.86	2.51	2.57
24.	6-MeO	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	79	123	48.01	48.17	3.41	3.31
25.	6-EtO	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	81	122	49.24	49.37	3.53	3.65
26.	4-Me	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	76	115	50.19	50.06	3.54	3.44
27.	5-Me	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	80	118	49.94	50.03	3.34	3.44
28.	6-Me	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	76	130	49.89	50.06	3.27	3.44
29.	4-Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	81	117	44.73	44.86	2.47	2.57
30.	5-Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	58	114	44.92	44.86	2.69	2.57
31.	6-Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	57	135	44.69	44.86	2.44	2.57
32.	6-MeO	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	57	120	48.04	48.17	3.15	3.31
33.	6-EtO	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂ S ₂	72	90	49.21	49.37	3.57	3.65

[(Substituted-2-benzothiazolyl) carbamoyl]methyl dithiocarbanilates: A mixture of (0.01 M) chloroacetylaminobenzothiazole and (0.01 M) ammonium salt of aryl dithiocarbamic acid [(I), R=H] in dry acetone was stirred for half an hour at room temperature and then heated under reflux for 90 minutes. Excess acetone was distilled off and the reaction product was washed thoroughly with distilled water and dried. The product was recrystallised from ethanol to obtain pure samples of the required product in 72% yield, m.p. 160°. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃N₂OS₂: C, 54.49; H, 3.62%. Found: C, 54.27; H, 3.60%. IR (nujol): 3450(w), 3200(w), 1720(s), 1620(s), 1585(m), 1370(s), 1065(m) cm⁻¹. NMR (CDCl₃): δ: 4.05 (2H, s), 7.00 to 7.80 for aromatic protons.

Similarly other [(substituted-2-benzothiazolyl)-carbamoyl]methyl-*o*, *m* or *p*-chlorodithiocarbanilates were prepared. Their yields, melting points and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Pharmacological screening: These compounds were screened for fungicidal activity on *Alternaria alternata* and *Aspergillus niger* at different dilutions. The results are summarised in Table 2.

The fungicidal screening was carried out by determining the percentage inhibition of colonial growth in comparison to the growth in controls¹⁷. All solutions were prepared in acetone and the medium in the treated plates was potato dextrose agar culture medium and the incubation time was 96 hrs at 28±1°.

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL AND INSECTICIDAL ACTIVITY OF [(SUBSTITUTED-2-BENZOTHAZOLYL)CARBAMOYL]METHYL (OR, *o, m* OR *p*-CHLORO)DITHIOCARBANILATES

No.	Substituents X	Y	%Inhibition of <i>Alternaria alternata</i>		%Inhibition of <i>Aspergillus niger</i>		%mortality of flies after 8 hours
			Dilutions		Dilutions		
			1: 2500	1: 5000	1: 2500	1: 5000	
1.	H	H	100	86	71	56	79
2.	4-Me	H	80	43	51	37	85
3.	5-Me	H	48	14	46	27	76
4.	6-Me	H	100	14	65	31	91
5.	4-Cl	H	71	60	67	64	87
6.	5-Cl	H	60	63	66	69	69
7.	6-Cl	H	100	86	77	56	93
8.	6-MeO	H	29	20	47	39	87
9.	6-EtO	H	43	40	39	23	80
10.	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	100	87	25	52	93
11.	4-Me	<i>o</i> -Cl	100	81	100	100	73
12.	5-Me	<i>o</i> -Cl	83	62	25	38	60
13.	6-Me	<i>o</i> -Cl	100	100	100	83	80
14.	4-Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	100	100	100	83	87
15.	5-Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	100	100	100	78	93
16.	6-MeO	<i>o</i> -Cl	100	67	38	57	80
17.	6-EtO	<i>o</i> -Cl	100	87	63	74	73
18.	4-Me	<i>m</i> -Cl	100	100	50	83	80
19.	5-Me	<i>m</i> -Cl	100	100	64	78	87
20.	6-Me	<i>m</i> -Cl	100	100	75	88	87
21.	4-Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	100	100	100	100	93
22.	5-Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	100	100	100	100	73
23.	6-Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	100	100	100	100	80
24.	6-MeO	<i>m</i> -Cl	100	100	100	100	93
25.	6-EtO	<i>m</i> -Cl	100	100	100	100	93
26.	4-Me	<i>p</i> -Cl	100	100	100	100	73
27.	5-Me	<i>p</i> -Cl	100	38	100	100	87
28.	6-Me	<i>p</i> -Cl	100	100	100	50	60
29.	4-Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	100	100	100	100	87
30.	5-Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	100	100	100	83	93
31.	6-Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	83	100	60	39	87
32.	6-MeO	<i>p</i> -Cl	100	67	100	67	87
33.	6-EtO	<i>p</i> -Cl	78	48	100	50	80

From the observations it is evident that the dithiocarbamates are capable of inhibiting fungal growth to a considerable extent both at high and low dilutions. Compound Nos ; 13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 20-26, 29 and 30 cause 100% inhibition of *Alternaria alternata* spores at both the dilutions when the benzothiazole nucleus is unsubstituted or has chloro group in it (*o, m, p*). Nine compounds (Nos : 11, 21-27 and 29) cause 100% inhibition of *Aspergillus niger* at both the dilutions proving them to be potent fungicides.

Insecticidal activity of some of the synthesised compounds was tested against *Musca domestica*. The compound (50 mg) was mixed with moist sugar (1 g) and was administered to the flies orally and their activity observed. A control containing the same number of flies fed on moist sugar was also set up.

It was observed that Compound Nos : 1, 5, 6, 10-12, 15, 16, 18, 21 and 23 exhibited appreciable insecticidal activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Mr. Sunil K. Singh, Junior Research Fellow, Department of Botany, D.A.V.(P.G.) College for fungicidal screening and Dr. Ram Lakhan, Reader in Organic Chemistry, BHU, Varanasi for valuable help and encouragement. Thanks are also due to the authorities of D.A.V.(P.G.) College, Dehra Dun for providing necessary facilities and to the CSIR, New Delhi, for

awarding a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (S.K.S.).

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